

Building An African Water Observatory From Open Data

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Abstract: Effective decision-making in water resource management is crucial for addressing the sustainability challenges exacerbated by climate change. This paper introduces an AI-driven observatory that integrates diverse data sources, including news outlets, social media, academic research, and statistical analyses, to enhance the decision-making capabilities of water resource managers and policymakers in North Africa. The observatory leverages advanced data visualization tools to provide in-depth analyses of water-related events such as floods, droughts, and contamination incidents. By drawing on real-time data from a variety of platforms, the system not only informs resource management and policy development but also plays a vital role in educating the public and preparing the youth for AI challenges. The focus of this paper is particularly on the Maghreb region, where the increasing frequency of extreme weather events due to climate change underscores the need for innovative approaches to water sustainability. We discuss the specific application of this observatory in promoting water reuse practices in the region, highlighting its potential to mitigate the impacts of such climatic extremes.

Keywords: Open Data; Artificial Intelligence; Extreme Events; Water Sustainability

INTRODUCTION

The data-driven digital transformation across industries and evidence-based decision making by the leadership across companies and local/national authorities is gaining its momentum worldwide and its reaching the African continent that has been much affected by Climate Change. It is therefore essential to highlight the meaningfulness of those approaches and technologies made available in the water sector as well, one of the priorities of many African countries. To leverage the awareness of the sector to the advantage of the insightful information provided by openly available data, complementing the specific knowledge of proprietary data collected in-house, we have developed a Water Observatory (accessible at naiades.ijs.si), based on well-established text mining and machine learning technologies. Water Observatory allows the user to interact through the appropriate data visualizations with large bodies of knowledge collected in real-time (e.g., worldwide news and social media) or frequently updated (e.g., published research, patents and indicators) to impact their policies and actions.

Most of the technologies available in the market today are geolocation-based ingesting sensor and satellite image data to enable real-time monitoring of resources and usage (Pita Costa et al, 2021). Global initiatives also exist to monitor the state of extreme events like floods and landslides in relation to Earth observation (Mikoš et al, 2022). The importance of these technologies as sustainable development tools is very significant, with water being directly or indirectly related to all UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) for 2030 (Casale and Cordeiro Ortigara 2019). Their role is therefore particularly important in the context of SDG 6 focusing on clean water and sanitation. It was mentioned by the UN secretary-general in April 2020 as "badly off track" although the several efforts done in this context so far (Blazhevaska, 2020).

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Figure 1 The ingestion of national statistical data allowing to compare in time the progress of regions in the south of Spain in the reused water against the available and supplied drinking water.

The water observatory presented in this paper was designed to serve the different stakeholders in the Water Sector, and built with some of them to better address their different workflows and priorities. The water resource managers are using the information generated by the observatory in the resolution of problems related to water events, to understand how their actions are perceived by the consumers, and to explore successful scenarios in similar cases. On the other hand, policy-makers in local authorities can use this system to help better align to the SDG 6 and to other European and national guidelines, in the context of evidence-based decision-making using open data, and evaluate commitments in time (see example of regional observation in figure 1). This technology allows to explore causality between indicators exploring the impact that they have in one another. We are also exploring trends and behaviour of seasons impacted by climate change based in the historical and forecasted availability of resources empowering preparedness.

Taking into account the role of Smart Water in the urban strategy (Casale and Cordeiro Ortigara 2019), such tool is useful to explore the several dimensions of data that expose the progress towards a *Smart Water City*. The further engagement with other stakeholders in the water sector through the access to data improves the business intelligence shared, and contributes to overcome key barriers to digitalisation as declared in (IWA & Xylem, 2019). Furthermore, this Water Observatory can also be used to explore water resources over relations between states, and also at a global level, to follow the water-related news and the main research topics. This can be useful in the context of Water Education, either in the classroom, complementing the didactical programme in schools, or towards the citizens in, e.g., the water museum of Alicante where we show further information on water events and the commitment of stakeholders.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Aiming to generate business intelligence from open data, this water observatory contributes to a holistic water ecosystem for digitisation of urban water sector. It has four views representing the insights that can be obtained from the exploration of indicators, media, research and the observation of natural resources. It consolidates a big diversity of open data, at a global and a local granularity, getting ingested into the system with different frequency, and powered by the most recent text mining, machine learning and data visualization methods. The amount and heterogeneity of data generated, coupled with the rapid progress of scientific research and

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of the news on water topics in 2023 in Mozambique relate to the concern of climate change (see figure 3). This is done by the automated classification of the ingested news text into the DMOZ taxonomy, allowing also to improve the queries to the dataset (Leban et al, 2014).

Figure 3 The exploration of news articles on water in Mozambique in 2023 shows that one of the biggest concerns is climate change, occupying 2% of the news topics space (on the left); and the sentiment analysis of the posts in the social network X during 2021, reflecting the overall public perception on the topic of floods in South Africa (on the right).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

With the advantage of Big Data, trends and best practices can be derived from the insightful query over news and research on a certain water topic. The resourceful dataset of media publications (including blogs) and scientific publications are helpful in exploring best practices and resolutions from success stories in, e.g., water contamination by *Escherichia Coli* (40 thousand media articles and seven thousand research papers). Moreover, we can use that combined knowledge base to investigate on wastewater management, exploring best practices in parallel to patented technologies (see figure 2) and to the animated visualization of research and technological trends across time (see figure 4).

Moreover, the real-time perspective of the water events exemplifies how we can leverage public opinion on alerting for water events and potentially defining alerts based on thresholds nowcasting the social media X (formally known as Twitter) triggered by other data source as, e.g., weather (Pita Costa et al, 2021). Through the X dashboard the user can further explore relations identified in the data, restrict to a certain time window and optimize the search query. The sentiment analysis helps gain awareness on the public opinion in, e.g., the rapid action to water events as floods happening in South Africa in 2021, that obtained a large positive sentiment in the social media X, much related with the way local authorities solved the problem (see figure 3).

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Figure 4 The concepts related with wastewater in the literature (provided by the Microsoft Academic Graph) through time, helping us to identify trends in research.

Climate change is a global issue that has been in the focus of Worldwide strategies in recent years, and the priorities are rapidly changing towards sustainability and environmental efficiency, transversely to most domains of action. The topic of Water has an important role in the context of climate change preparedness, where technologies like the NAIADES Water Observatory presented in this paper can provide significant contribution. Already from the appropriate exploration of worldwide news it is noticeable the increase of reported events on the climate change and its impact on water resources. This reflects, in a time window between January 2021 and November 2022, more than 590 thousand news articles with increasingly higher peaks, and including concepts as drought (116602) and flood (108987), or temperature (85411) and global warming (85922).

Building upon common interests, exciting initiatives, and existing projects developed by IRCAI and AI in Africa, we have developed a set of challenges focused on AI and Water Sustainability. This activity aims to build capacity within African youth to advance the Sustainable Development Goals through AI on challenges within their own communities and in the region. It comes in the context of discussions directed to a final event in GITEX Africa in May 2023 that puts together experts from AI and Water domains, directed to Youth in AI, including students and young entrepreneurs working for the good of their communities. The global challenge of this action, "Water, AI and Sustainability" is one of the MENA priorities and follows the work done by IRCAI (see report <https://ircai.org/project/ircais-project-report-on-naiades/> and pilot <http://naiades.ircai.org/>). This collaboration around technologies and shifts of the future is an initiative designed to encourage a conversation between the communities, corporate thought leaders, the education visionaries, and the ecosystems builders to have constructive conversations around the needs of the changing future landscape. The discussions include start-up communities, technologists, and government representatives to unite and define the future as they see it.

CONCLUSIONS

The results presented in this study highlight insights that can be obtained from open data pertaining to relevant water topics such as water contamination, extreme water events, wastewater management or climate change preparedness. The complementary nature of diverse data sources offering different perspectives of the same topic with regional granularity, enabling insightful assessment that contributes to the enhancement of the business intelligence of water utilities and local authorities, but also towards better informed, empowered and engaged communities.

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